

Experimental and Numerical Study of Steel-faced Profiled Sandwich Panels with PIR Core Loaded in Flexure

Shekhar Silwal^{*,a}, Kristo Mela^a, Zhongcheng Ma^b

^aTampere University of Technology, Faculty of Built Environment, Finland
shekhar.silwal@tuni.fi, kristo.mela@tuni.fi

^bHäme University of Applied Sciences, Finland
zhongcheng.ma@hamk.fi

ABSTRACT

This study investigates the mechanical response of steel-faced sandwich panels with one strongly profiled face and having polyisocyanurate (PIR) as core material. This paper aims to study the effect of a profiled face that has a completely bonded face-core interface on the overall shear resistance of the sandwich panel. A series of small-scale tests were devised and conducted on sandwich panel beam specimens that were prepared by cutting the panel to include only one profiled part from its full width. The experiments were carried out using 2-point loading and 4-point loading testing methods. Material tests for the mechanical characterization of each component of the sandwich panel were also conducted following EN 14509:2013. The obtained experimental results are compared with the results from numerical analysis performed in ABAQUS software. The paper will present detailed test results, offering an extensive analysis of the structural response, including insights into failure modes and resistance.

Keywords: Sandwich panel, Shear strength, PIR, Shear modulus

1 INTRODUCTION

Structural sandwich panels are made up of two thin metal (usually steel) facings that enclose a thicker core with low density material which has good insulation properties. These panels are often used in the construction of industrial, commercial, and residential buildings. When designing a sandwich panel, it is crucial to consider all potential failure modes that could occur within the steel faces and core. When the panel is introduced with at least one or both faces with profiles an additional failure can occur due to the shear strength acting on the webs of profiles and the support reaction capacity of a profiled face (1).

To determine the shear strength capacity of a profiled sandwich panel, the European Standard EN14509:2013 (2) recommends using a small-scale shear beam extracted from the flat part of the panel. However, this approach limits the consideration of the profiled face's influence on the overall shear strength capacity. As an alternative to the shear beam test, EN 14509:2013 suggested conducting a full-scale test using the entire width of the panel. This method can provide comprehensive insights into the force transfer between the profiled face and the core. However, the full-scale test is complex to execute, and visualizing the failure mode is challenging as the sandwich specimen is tested while covered. A previous study (3) on a profiled sandwich panel with a mineral wool core, which was incompletely bonded to the profiled face, demonstrated that the shear stress acting on the webs of profiles caused distortional buckling and local crushing of the core within the unbonded area. In a typical profiled sandwich panel with a foam core, the profiled face is fully bonded to the core material. This bonding leads to a concentration of stresses in the bonded area, potentially resulting in various failure modes. Hence, there is a need for a study to examine the role of profiled

faces in resisting shear force and the potential failure modes that may occur in a sandwich panel where the profiled face and core are fully bonded.

This paper presents an experimental and numerical investigation of sandwich panels with one steel face strongly profiled and a Polyisocyanurate (PIR) foam core. The objective is to examine the role of the profiled part of the top face in resisting shear loads. The approach is to perform classical shear beam tests, where the specimen contains the profiled part of the top face. Usually, the shear beam specimens are cut from the panel without the profiled part. Two loading arrangements are applied namely 2-point and 4-point loading. The study provides an in-depth analysis of the distribution of shear force and bending moment between the profiled face and the PIR core of the sandwich panels. When the sandwich beam is loaded in flexure, it can fail by different modes, mainly core shear, face yielding and wrinkling of steel faces. A Finite Element Analysis (FEA) is also conducted to visualize the critical stress areas and to compare these with the experimentally observed failure modes.

2 EXPERIMENTAL PROGRAM

2.1 Test specimens

The tests were performed on sandwich panels with PIR core (bulk density of 37 kg/m) and a strongly profiled top face. The panel facings were composed of a thin steel sheet (steel grade = S280GD) with a nominal thickness of 0,5 mm. The external face of the panel was strongly profiled, while the internal face was flat (or slightly profiled). For testing, panels with two different core thicknesses, d_c , were considered. These panels had a common trapezoidal face depth, d_{trape} , of 40 mm. The panels with core thicknesses of 100 mm and 170 mm were named R-PIR 140/100 and R-PIR 210/170, respectively. The test used a small beam specimen extracted from the full width of the panel, which included at least one profiled part, as depicted in Fig. 1. The sample was carefully cut without affecting the bonding between the core and the steel facings.

Fig. 1. Cross-section of test specimens

2.2 Mechanical characterization

Uniaxial compression and simple shear tests were conducted on the PIR core of the sandwich panel. These tests were carried out on a Zwick Roell tensile testing machine at room temperature (23 °C). The compression test was conducted in accordance with the guidelines provided in the standard EN 826 (4), resulting in a force-displacement curve as depicted in Fig. 2a.

Fig. 2. Material test a) Compression test; b) Shear test

In the graph, the initial region represents the linear elastic regime. The slope of this linear part was utilized to compute the Young’s modulus of the PIR foam. Transitioning into the second phase, a

plateau region is observed. This plateau signifies the collapse of the cell walls of the foam, leading to a rapid increase in strain with only a slight increase in load. In the final phase, the collapsed cell walls undergo densification, causing a significant increase in stiffness.

A simple shear test of the PIR foam according to the standard EN 12090 (5) was conducted in order to obtain the shear strength of the core material, which in this work is required to establish the material model of the PIR core for finite element analysis. Three tests were conducted for each panel type. A rectangular sample with dimensions of $100 \times 95 \times 20$ mm was prepared and acclimated at room temperature for 24 hours. A tensile testing machine applied a displacement-controlled tensile load from the upper crosshead at a rate of 2 mm/min, while the lower end was fixed. The test continued until a clear shear failure occurred, as shown in Fig. 2b. Measured properties of the PIR core are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Measured values of foam density (ρ), compressive elastic modulus (E_c), shear strength (τ), compressive strength (F_{Cc}) and their corresponding standard deviations (SD)

Panel types	ρ [kg/m ³]	E_c [MPa]	SD	τ [MPa]	SD	F_{Cc} [MPa]	SD
R-PIR 140/100	37	2,92	0,16	0,14	0,01	0,11	0,01
R-PIR 210/170	37	3,1	0,17	0,15	0,01	0,12	0,02

Tensile tests were performed on both types of panel facings in accordance with EN ISO 6892-1:2019 (6). For each type of facing, three coupons were utilized. These were extracted from the flat section of the flange. The results of these tests are presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Measured values of yield strength of profiled face (f_{y1}), yield strength of flat face (f_{y2}), steel-facing thickness of upper profiled face (t_{F1}), steel-facing thickness of lower flat face (t_{F2}), and their corresponding standard deviations (SD)

Panel types	f_{y1} [MPa]	SD	f_{y2} [MPa]	SD	t_{F1} [mm]	t_{F2} [mm]
R-PIR 140/100	442	9,54	452	22,36	0,40	0,36
R-PIR 210/170	433	3,60	385	4,51	0,41	0,43

2.3 Test methods

The short beam test was conducted using two different loading configurations: a 2-point loading test and a 4-point loading test, as depicted in Fig. 3. For each type of panel, three samples were prepared and tested. In the 2-point loading test, the span length of the beam specimen was determined in accordance with EN 14509:2013 (2) where the free distance between the loading plate and the support plate was based on the core thickness ($\leq 1,2 \times d_c$).

Fig. 3. Test setup a) 2-point loading test; b) 4-point loading test

The span length for the 4-point loading was determined based on the test setup outlined in the authors' previous work (3). Table 3 provides the dimensional guidelines for the test setup.

Table 3. Details on the dimensions used for test methods.

Panel name	2-point loading test		4-point loading test	
	R-PIR 140/100	R PIR 210/170	R-PIR 140/100	R PIR 210/170
Span length, L [mm]	810	1212	1160	1328
Width of support plate [mm]	150	200	150	200
Width of outer loading plate [mm]	150	200	200	200
Width of inner loading plates [mm]	-	-	150	150

In all the 4-point loading test setups, the free distance between the two inner loading plates was set to 10 mm, while the distance between the inner and outer loading plates was set to 5 mm. During the test, a displacement transducer was positioned at the mid-point of the beam to record the mid-span displacement, denoted as w . A displacement-controlled load was applied at a rate of 3 mm/min.

In addition, a full-scale shear test was performed on the full width of the panel using a vacuum box to act as a reference test method, following the standard EN 14509:2013 (2). For the full-scale test, five test samples of R-PIR 140/100 with a span length of 1,4 m were tested and three test samples of R-PIR 210/170 with a span length of 1,7m were tested. The primary objective of the full-scale test was to determine the shear modulus and shear strength, which would then be compared with the results from the beam test. The shear modulus, G_c , obtained from the full-scale test was utilized in the calculations in all test cases.

3 ANALYTICAL SOLUTION

The analytical solution is based on the fundamental sandwich theory available in the literature (1), (7) and (8). Only the relevant formulas required for the calculation are provided here. A detailed analytical solution for 2-point and 4-point loading configurations is outlined in a separate work by the authors (3). It is assumed that the force resultants in a profiled sandwich panel are separated between steel faces and core (9). Since the bending stiffness of a flat face, B_{F2} , is almost negligible, only the bending stiffness of a profiled face, B_{F1} , is considered in the total bending stiffness, B_F . The bending stiffness of a profiled face can be calculated as:

$$B_{F1} = E_{F1}I_{F1} \quad (1)$$

where E_{F1} is Young's modulus of the profiled face and I_{F1} is the moment of inertia with respect to the centroid of the profiled face.

The bending stiffness, B_s , of the panel due to the sandwich effect can be calculated as:

$$B_s = \frac{E_{F1}A_{F1}E_{F2}A_{F2}}{E_{F1}A_{F1} + E_{F2}A_{F2}} e^2 \quad (2)$$

where e is the distance between the centroids of the faces, E_{F2} is Young's modulus of the flat steel face, A_{F1} is the area of the profiled steel face, and A_{F2} is the area of the flat steel face.

For a point load applied within the span length, L , of the beam at a location x ($\varepsilon = x/L$) the component of shear force, V , and bending moment, M , can be calculated as (1):

$$V_{S1} = \frac{F}{(1 + \alpha)} \left[1 - \varepsilon - \frac{\sinh\lambda(1 - \varepsilon)}{\sinh\lambda} \cosh\lambda\xi \right] \quad (3)$$

$$V_{S2} = \frac{F}{(1 + \alpha)} \left[-\varepsilon + \frac{\sinh\lambda\varepsilon}{\sinh\lambda} \cosh\lambda(1 - \xi) \right] \quad (4)$$

$$V_{F1} = \frac{F\alpha}{(1 + \alpha)} \left[1 - \varepsilon + \frac{\sinh\lambda(1 - \varepsilon)}{\alpha\sinh\lambda} \cosh\lambda\xi \right] \quad (5)$$

$$V_{F2} = \frac{F\alpha}{(1 + \alpha)} \left[-\varepsilon - \frac{\sinh\lambda\varepsilon}{\alpha\sinh\lambda} \cosh\lambda(1 - \xi) \right] \quad (6)$$

$$M_{S1} = \frac{FL}{(1 + \alpha)} \left[\xi(1 - \varepsilon) - \frac{\sinh\lambda(1 - \varepsilon)}{\lambda\sinh\lambda} \sinh\lambda\xi \right] \quad (7)$$

$$M_{S2} = \frac{FL}{(1 + \alpha)} \left[\varepsilon(1 - \xi) - \frac{\sinh\lambda\varepsilon}{\lambda\sinh\lambda} \sinh\lambda(1 - \xi) \right] \quad (8)$$

$$M_{F1} = \frac{FL\alpha}{(1 + \alpha)} \left[(1 - \varepsilon)\xi + \frac{\sinh\lambda(1 - \varepsilon)}{\alpha\lambda\sinh\lambda} \sinh\lambda\xi \right] \quad (9)$$

$$M_{F2} = \frac{FL\alpha}{(1 + \alpha)} \left[\varepsilon(1 - \xi) + \frac{\sinh\lambda\varepsilon}{\alpha\lambda\sinh\lambda} \sinh\lambda(1 - \xi) \right] \quad (10)$$

where $\alpha = B_F/B_S$, $\lambda = \sqrt{(1 + \alpha)/(\alpha\beta)}$ in which $\beta = B_S d_c / B e^2 G_c L^2$

In Eqs. (3-10), the subscripts S and F represent the sandwich and steel facing respectively and index 1 is valid for $0 \leq \varepsilon \leq \zeta$ (i.e. left to the load) and index 2 for $\varepsilon \leq \zeta \leq 1$ (i.e. right to the load).

The maximum value of shear force is attained close to the support plate which can be calculated by setting $\zeta=0$ whereas the bending moment is maximum at mid-span which can be calculated by setting $\zeta=0,5$. Once the total shear force, V_s , acting on the core due to point loads (2 points or 4 points) is determined, the shear stress, f_{cv} , acting across the width, B , of the core can be calculated as:

$$f_{cv} = \frac{V_s}{Be} \quad (11)$$

Finally, the maximum bending moment, which acts on both the sandwich and the steel facing at the mid-span of the panel, can be used to calculate the wrinkling strength, σ_w , as:

$$\sigma_w = \frac{M_s}{eA_{F1}} + \frac{M_F E_{F1} e_{11}}{B_F} \quad (12)$$

4 FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS

A finite element analysis (FEA) of the sandwich beam was constructed using the software Abaqus/Explicit to understand the distribution of stress within the sandwich components. The geometry and dimensions of the sandwich beam were the same as those given in Table 3. The core was modelled using C3D8 (8-node linear brick) elements whereas the facings were modelled using shell element S4R (4-node, reduced integration). As there was no delamination or slip observed during the test, a tie contact was used to define the interaction between the core and steel faces which will cause identical displacement between the tied nodes. The wooden loading plates were used to apply the load on the beam in a similar manner as depicted in Fig. 3. The plates were modelled as linear elastic using the properties of the wood (10). General contact with a friction coefficient of 0,4 (11) was used to define the contact between the loading wooden plates and the sandwich beams.

The steel facing was modelled as ideal elastic-plastic with linear hardening. The hardening data was defined using the true stress-strain data derived from the engineering stress-strain results obtained from the tensile coupon tests. The properties of steel facings are given in Table 2. The elastic part was defined using the elastic modulus of 210 GPa and Poisson's ratio of 0,3. For PIR foam, the initial elastic part was specified by the linear elastic material model. Poisson's ratio of zero was used as for most of the foam material the Poisson's ratio is almost negligible (12). The plastic part of PIR foam was defined using a crushable foam model with isotropic hardening (13) where the yield surface is defined as:

$$F = \sqrt{q^2 + \alpha^2 p^2} - \sigma_c \sqrt{1 + \left(\frac{\alpha}{3}\right)^2} = 0 \quad (13)$$

where q is the von Mises stress, p is the pressure stress, σ_c is the yield stress in compression and α is the shape factor of the yield ellipse which can be expressed as

$$\alpha = 3k/\sqrt{9 - k^2} \quad (14)$$

where k is the ratio of initial yield stress in compression to the initial yield hydrostatic stress. However, the hydrostatic compressive stress is difficult to obtain due to the complexity of the test arrangement. Alternatively, for an approximately elliptic yielding surface, the value of k was determined using the obtained value of ultimate shear strength from the shear test as (14):

$$k = \sqrt{9 - 9(\sigma_c/\tau)} \quad (15)$$

Using the measured values of Table 1 in Eq. 3, the compressive yield stress ratio of the PIR foam was obtained to be approximately 1,28. The hardening law was defined using the yield stress obtained from the uniaxial compression test as a function of the absolute value of the axial plastic strain. A

mesh convergence study was carried out using element sizes of 5 mm and 10 mm where no significant changes were observed in the force-displacement response. Therefore, to enhance computational efficiency and given the absence of damage in the finite element model, the mesh size of 10 mm was used for the validation of the material model which involved a comparison between the results of the FE model and the compression test of the core material of the panel type R-PIR 140/100. This comparison showed a satisfactory level of agreement, as illustrated in Fig. 4(a). The boundary condition for the flexure loading condition is depicted in Fig. 4(b). The load was applied on a wooden plate using a reference point that had a set of coupled nodes along the mid-plane at the rate of 2 mm/s. To replicate the flexure loading condition similar to the test, both support plates are allowed to rotate along the X-axis, while the support plate on the right side is allowed to translate along the Z-axis (see Fig. 4).

Fig. 4. a) Comparison of experimental and FEA results of compression test; b) FE model with the boundary conditions

5 RESULTS

Results from the 2-point and 4-point loading tests are summarized in Table 4. For both R-PIR 140/100 and R-PIR 210/170 panel types, a similar level of ultimate load was recorded in both loading configurations. However, the span length of the sandwich beam in the 4-point loading test is longer than in the 2-point loading test, necessitating a comprehensive examination of the total load distributed between the profiled face and the core.

Table 4. Summary of mean values from of ultimate load, F_u , core shear stress, f_{cv} , and wrinkling strength, σ_w , with their corresponding standard deviations, SD.

Test type	Panel type	F_u [kN]	SD	f_{cv} [MPa]	SD	σ_w [MPa]	SD
2-point loading	R-PIR 140/100	11,08	0,61	0,116	0,009	76,06	5,56
	R-PIR 210/170	14,72	0,29	0,112	0,001	111,92	1,53
4-point loading	R-PIR 140/100	10,87	0,44	0,123	0,006	110,28	5,88
	R-PIR 210/170	14,07	0,20	0,116	0,001	120,69	1,55
Full-scale	R-PIR 140/100	43,30	2,90	0,114	0,015	171,55	8,01
	R-PIR 210/170	55,35	4,40	0,101	0,101	151,10	17,04

Fig. 5 illustrates the distribution of the total shear force between the core and the profiled face for each test method.

Fig. 5. Distribution of shear force between the core and profiled face

The calculation of internal force distribution in each component was calculated using Eqs. (3-10). It can be seen that the core of the thicker panel (R-PIR 210/170) tends to resist a higher level of shear force. Conversely, for the thinner panel (R-PIR 140/100), the profiled face also plays a significant role in resisting a substantial amount of force under 2-point loading and the full-scale test. Further detailed analysis of the total force distribution between the core and profiled face can be accessed by plotting a shear force and bending moment diagram. This was done for the panel type R-PIR 140/100 and R-PIR 210/170 using the ultimate load obtained from the test, as shown in Fig. 6 and Fig. 7 respectively.

Fig. 6. Bending moment and shear force diagram for panel type R-PIR 140/100: a) 2-point load; b) 4-point load

Fig. 7. Bending moment and shear force diagram for panel type PIR 210/170: a) 2-point load; b) 4-point load

This diagram demonstrates the variation in the distribution of the total shear force into the profiled face and core, as well as the bending moment along the span of the sandwich beam in both loading configurations. It was observed that the webs of the profiled face resisted a higher level of shear force in the 2-point loading test than in the 4-point loading test. On the other hand, in the 4-point loading test, the core of the sandwich beam was subjected to a higher level of shear stress. Additionally, the bending moment was found to be higher in the case of the 4-point test.

A similar failure mode was observed across all test cases with preliminary local buckling of the upper flange of the profiled face. It was observed that both tests experienced a sudden drop in force, attributable to preliminary buckling. Despite this initial buckling, the sandwich beam continued to withstand additional load until it demonstrated post-buckling behavior, ultimately leading to failure. To analyse this failure mode, only one test from each method was considered. These tests were then compared with the Finite Element Analysis (FEA), as depicted by the force-displacement curve in Fig. 8.

Fig. 8. Comparison between experimental and FEA analysis a)2-point loading test of R-PIR 210/170; b)4-point loading test of R-PIR 140/100

The common failure mode observed in the 2-point loading test of R-PIR 210/170 is depicted in Fig. 9. The failure appears to have initiated with the preliminary local buckling of the upper flange of the profiled face, located beneath the loading plates followed by the wrinkling of the lower flange as an ultimate failure mode. In the two-point loading test, cracks were noticed on the trapezoidal area of the foam core at the end of the specimen.

Fig. 9. Common failure mode observed in the 2-point loading of R-PIR 210/170 along with FEA results

This was also observed in the case of panel type R-PIR 140/100. This indicates that the shear force resisted by the webs of the profile was transferred to the foam core, which served as an elastic foundation. The FEA shows the potential failure region by demonstrating the stress level withstood by the core in the area where the crack initiated and propagated. Here, in the FE model, at the stress concentration area of the webs of profile and the foam, the foam element is subjected to compressive stress (y-direction) of 0,173 MPa, which exceeds the measured ultimate compressive stress of the PIR foam (refer to Table 1). The compressive stress in the core above the support plate area was 0,134 MPa which is also higher than the compressive strength of the core material. This indicates there was a possible failure by local crushing of the core on the support plate. However, no damage criteria were defined in the FEA, and as a result, the cracks and wrinkling failure were not observed. Both panel types when tested with 4-point loading failed primarily with local buckling of the upper flange followed by buckling of the lower flange of the profiled face as the ultimate failure. There were no visible cracks of the core material observed in the 4-point loading test in any of the test specimens. The stress distribution across the core of the panel type R-PIR 140/100 is shown in Fig. 10.

Fig. 10. Failure mode observed during the 4-point loading test conducted on R-PIR 140/100 along with the distribution of the von Mises stress in the PIR core predicted by FEA

6 CONCLUSION

The results show that the profiled sandwich beams with PIR core with both 100 mm and 170 mm core thickness failed preliminary by local buckling of the upper flange of the steel profile under both 2-point and 4-point loading configurations. This leads to the conclusion that the short beam test method utilized in this study is not suitable for determining the shear strength of the core, because clear shear failure is not obtained. However, it can be employed to investigate the role of the profiled face in resisting the total shear force.

The results indicate that for profiled sandwich beams with PIR cores of 100 mm and 170 mm thicknesses, the core thickness significantly influences shear force resistance. The panel with the thinner core experienced a higher level of shear stress in the webs of the profiled face, while the panel with the thicker core predominantly resisted the shear force. It can be concluded that the compressive strength of the foam core significantly contributes to the overall mechanical performance of the sandwich panel. The foam core served as an elastic foundation, resisting the concentrated shear stress acting across the webs of the profile.

The distribution of bending moment between the core and the profiled face varies depending on the loading configuration, which affects the ultimate load and failure mode of the sandwich beams. The 4-point loading test resulted in a higher level of bending strength of the panel failing them with local buckling at mid-span. In 2-point loading, there was a wrinkling failure as a post-buckling behavior.

The results demonstrate that the FEA can accurately predict the load-displacement behavior and the potential failure region of the sandwich beams. However, to accurately represent the yielding sections along with the failure, including cracks and wrinkling, it is necessary to incorporate failure criteria into the FE model, which is currently lacking.

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